

INTERPRETATION OF NAVRUZ IN UZBEK POETRY

Fozilova O‘g‘iloy Fayoz qizi

Bukhara State University 2st year PhD. Student

ugiloyfozilova21@gmail.com

Annotation: Nowruz holiday has been considered a farming holiday since ancient times. Spring crops begin directly with the arrival of Nowruz. After a few days, the farmer takes his hoe and rushes to his field. Work begins for the New Year's harvest. A solid ground is prepared for a blessed harvest during this period. Navoi was able to describe the beauty of the living nature and the beauty of the universe under the influence of divine power. The depiction of man and nature in this way is an artistic expression of the mystical view that they are an integral continuation of each other, a single, eternal and eternal mirror of beauty that complements each other.

Key words: nature, holiday, Navruz, uzbek folklore, traditions, spring, literature.

In the system of the most ancient spiritual traditions of our people, our traditions related to Navruz occupy a special place. The interpretation of Navruz, which is deeply embedded in the life and psyche of our people, is widely observed not only in oral literature, but also in written literature. In particular, the interpretation of our udums related to Navruz was expressed in a unique artistic way by our classic poets and put into poetry.

Works dedicated to Navruz in Uzbek classics were organized. However, they have not been identified in our science. However, classical epics, many compositions, and ghazals have been created about Navruz, so it is necessary to compare and study the characteristics of them, the similar and different aspects of waves in folklore. Because it provides information on topics related to the relationship between oral and written creativity. T.Mirzaev and M.Zhoraev compiled and published the collection “Navruz” which reflects folk examples related to Navruz in Uzbek folkloristics. In

2009, M. Joraev’s monograph “Navroz Bayram” was published. This year, familiar folklorists Jabbor Eshankulov and Shamirza Turdimov published a collection of “Navruz Nashidasi” containing proverbs, songs, and poems about spring. Along with representatives of classic poetry such as Mahmud Koshgari, Umar Khayom, Alisher Navoi, Babur, Ogahi, Furqat, Muqimi, there were also poetic works of modern lyrical artists dedicated to Navruz and Bahar songs.

In general, in Uzbek folklore and writing ability, in the period of Uzbek folklore and modern poetry, Navruz’s singing feature has its own unique breakthroughs. Comparative study of them is one of today’s urgent scientific problems.

The written literature, there was the experience of creating “Navruznoma” works. Umar Hayyom’s name is identified in this line. In his treatise, there are many customs, events, and legends related to Navruz holiday, and there are big differences between Navruz holiday at the time of their appearance and the Navruz holiday of the time described by Umar Hayyom.

In addition, Narshahi’s “History of Bukhara”, Abu Rayhan Beruni’s “Relics from Ancient Nations”, Ferdavsi’s “Shahnoma”, Mahmud Kashgari’s “Devonu lug’otit turk”, Alisher Navoi’s “Tarihi Muluki Ajam”, Hafiz Tanish Bukhari’s works are also worth attention in this regard. Pulls Because they contain the order of the Nowruz holiday, the content of legends and narratives about the origin of traditions related to it, and some historical information.

In the introduction of Yusuf Khos Hajib’s work “Qutadgu Bilig” there is a qasada dedicated to the spring song, while Haidar Khorezmi wrote the epic “Gul va Navruz” in 1411 by order of Sultan Iskandar. “Gul and Navruz” is a metaphorical epic about love. In it, Nowruz is artistically interpreted as a symbol of spring, and Flower as a symbol of nature.

Nasiruddin Rabguzi’s ghazal on the theme of Navruz has its place in classical poetry. The poet writes in it:

*Kun hamalga kirdi esa keldi olam Navro’zi,
Kechdi bahman, zamharir qish, qolmadi qori, buzi.
Kun kelu ming ko’rki ortib tirilur o’lmish jahon,*

Tong badizlab naqshi birla bezanur bu yer yuzi.

This ghazal expresses the feelings of a person who is happy with the arrival of Navruz, the awakening of nature, everything is covered with greenery and flowers, the end of cold days and the beginning of warm days. In the ghazal, Navruz symbols have become: It was song about the pleasant spring wind, the budding of trees, the hills covered with crimson tulips, and the return of cranes, geese, ducks, parrots, coots, nightingales, and swallows that had flown to far away warm lands in winter.

Alisher Navoi and Bobur also wrote a number of lyrical works about Navruz in classical ghazal. Mystical poets could not imagine the beauty of nature and man apart from their creator, original source. Because according to Sufism, God created the material world from his own body in order to see his beauty and the perfection of his body as in a mirror. The universe created beautiful nature and man. This is how nature and society came into being. These two polar parts of God's body began to live. Allah has made all the amazing signs of his beauty shine in nature and man. Existence - God's grace has appeared as a mirror. The image of the eternal God has turned into a shrine where His beauty is displayed and admired.

In Navroz's ghazal, the cypress tree was chosen as a generalized symbol of nature and human society, and the love of God was embedded in the interpretation of these symbols.

In Uzbek literature, especially in the period before Navoi, there are few ghazals specifically dedicated to Navruz song. In this respect, this ghazal was a unique artistic experience in its time. It occupies an important place in the development of the tradition of creating Navruz ghazals.

The artistic value of the ghazal is that the poet was able to create a comparative picture of the divine beauty by depicting the beloved human figure in harmony with nature. The poet chooses the scenery of the cypress tree as he chooses a fabric from the charming pictures of nature, comparing it to the human pleasure. He likens a person to a cypress, and a cypress to a person. Human qualities are revealed in the process of comparison with cypress. In particular, in the great poetic heritage of the

great Uzbek poet Alisher Navoi, one can find many artistic scenes about Navruz, Navruz holiday, the charming grace and life-giving freshness of spring in general.

Navoi often likens Spring, Navruz in general, to a beautiful mistress:

*Vasl aro ko'rdum, teng emish bo'yi-yu sochi,
Tun-kun teng ekan zohir o'lur, bo'ldi Navro'z.*

It is not for nothing that the poet compares the dark hair of the lover to the night and her beautiful white figure to the day. Because Nowruz is coming, the days are getting longer and the nights are getting shorter. Her hair is also shorter than her figure, you can look at the poet's information in the allegory. In fact, Khorezmi, from Navoi to Navoi, used this analogy in the work “Muhabbatnoma”.

It is known that on the days of Navruz, everyone says good words to each other, wishes good things, stops bad things, and wars and quarrels have risen to the level of folk tradition. Navoi is referring to this tradition with these verses in the form of applause. It is noteworthy that a ghazal with the same meaning is found in Bobur's works:

*Iloho, har kuning navro'z bo'lsin!
Hamisha toleying feruz bo'lsin!*

Ogahi, Muqimi and Furqat also have beautiful ghazals dedicated to Nowruz. Ogahi writes in the ghazal “Ey Nigor, kelmish bahor” to convey the essence of Navruz to the people, to make their plans right from the beginning of the year, and thus achieve a blessed New Year's Eve:

*Behuda o'tkazma fursat ushbu ayyom bexabar,
Bundan oldin ham ketib boz necha bor kelmish bahor.*

Furqat's gazals, which begin with “Fasli navbahor oldi, ketibon zimistonlar”, Muqimi's “Navbahor have already become the spiritual property and heart treasure of our people.

Bibliography:

1. Бўриев О. Наврўз тарихидан лавҳалар. – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 1990. – 64 с.
2. Жўраев М. Наврўз байрами. – Т.: Фан, 2009. – 230 б.
3. Наврўз нашидаси. Баҳор ҳақидаги мақол-айтим, кўшиқ ва шеърлар. Нашрга тайёрловчи ва сўзбоши муаллифлари Ж.Эшонқулов, Ш.Турдимов. – Т.: Фан, 2009. – 260 б.